

Topsy – Turvy condition of the illegal immigrants in Kiran Desai’s “The Inheritance of Loss”

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Abstract

Kiran Desai, one of the talented writers of our generation published her novel “The Inheritance of Loss” in 2006 and fetched the “2006 Man Booker Prize” for it. She highlighted the sufferings of the illegal immigrants in this novel. Some people build air castles and go abroad thinking they can spin money there. But things become topsy – turvy for them. They are kicked by people from one place to the other and they finally decide to fly back to their mother land. These aspects are highlighted by Kiran Desai in her novel “The Inheritance of Loss”

Twentieth century women’s writing was considered as a powerful medium of modernism and feminist statements. The last two decades have witnessed overflowing success in portraying the theme of immigration and consequent alienation of the self. This was the the metric pre-occupation of Indo-Anglian novelists like Jumpha Lahiri, Chitra Banerjee, Amitav Gosh and Kiran Desai. They are chiefly concerned with cross- cultural and racist encounters between the characters on socio-cultural plane.

Kiran Desai who was born of 3rd September 1971 at Delhi, is one of the talented writers of our generation. She is the daughter of Anita Desai. She wrote her first novel *Hullabaloo* in the *Guava – Orchard* in 1998. She was highly exalted for this work and she received a 1998 Betty Trask Prize from the British society of Authors. Eight years later, her second novel *The Inheritance of Loss* was published in early 2006 and won the 2006 Man Booker Award, the National Book critics Circle Fiction Award in 2007 and the 2006 vodafone crossword Book Award. Rajni Singh passed the following comments on the novel *The Inheritance of Loss*:

Desai tries to depict the subjugation and exploitation of immigrants from centuries by America, the economic super power of world. Post modern global economy has created drastic situation in the life of third world immigrants specially the predicaments of illegal immigrants are nerve shattering (198).

The Inheritance of Loss. follows the journey of Biju, an illegal immigrant in the U.S. who is trying to make a new life. This novel is set partly in India and partly in the U.S.A. Desai tries to capture what

it means to live between East and West and what it means to be an immigrant and she highlights how an illegal immigrant is fretting and fuming in a foreign land.

Jemubhai Patel, a retired judge lived with his chatty cook Nandu and with his granddaughter Sai. Nandu's only son worked as an illegal immigrant in various restaurants in New York. He moved from one place to another and sadly remembered his father and childhood days in a village in India.

The novel concentrated on the down scale immigrants who were leading a miserable and disrespectful life in America, with a staunch hope of a better future for his son. The cook, with his very meagre savings, planned to send his son to America. Biju too dreamt of establishing himself in an alien soil. In America, Biju leaped from one low paid restaurant job to another. The insensitive restaurant owners, not only exploited Biju, but also took every opportunity to degrade him which was the part of their power game.

At the Gandhi Café, Biju had close association with rats. They said "Halloo" and chewed his hair. He was having power of tolerance and he was able to bear with it. Kiran Desai vividly portrays how the rats played on him casually:

The rats of his earlier jobs had not forsaken Biju. They were here too, exulting in the garbage, clawing through wood, making holes... One chewed Biju's hair at night (147)

S. Nusrath Sulthana, in her "The Theme of Alienation and Identity Crisis in Kiran Desai's *The Inheritance of Loss* observes:

In New York, Biju finds himself cast in a strange world, a world where sympathy, fellow feeling and peaceful Co-existence does not seem to exist. He spends his time changing jobs, enduring deplorable conditions and trying to dodge the immigration authorities of the United States. As he is an illegal immigrant, he is forced to work for very few wages and experience extreme servitude to his employers.

At Pignocchio's Italian Restaurant, Biju had a tough time, in pleasing the owner's wife. The lady complained that Biju smelt Indian and that she was allergic to his hair oil. The lady's persistent grumbling and disgust for Biju, compelled him to seek a new job for himself. "He smells," said the owner's wife, "I think I am allergic to his hair oil" (48)

Kiran Desai had portrayed the impact of the politics of globalization and post colonialism on the economic structure of the once colonized nation. When an advertisement appeared in the local paper for drudge staff in America, Biju applied and attended the interview in Kathmandu, Nepal and finally got selected. Biju took some of the cook's fake recommendations with him to the interview to prove that he had come from an honest family and a letter from Father Pooty. When the Americans enquired, Biju had shown a fake bank statement procured by a cook from a corrupt State Bank Clerk in exchange of two bottles of Black Label. Desai presented this character "Biju" who got trapped in the vicious desire of becoming a 'big shot'. Saeed from Zanzibar, kavafya from kaza, Omar from Malaysia and Harish Harry from India endured the pain of exile with a smile. The illegal immigrants spent their time dodging the authorities and stood benumbed to the questions asked by them.

In New York, Biju worked in different restaurants as an illegal immigrant and thus encountered unhappy social as well as cultural experiences in the West:

Biju joined the shifting population of men camping out near the fuse box, behind the boiler in the cubby holes, and in old shaped corners that once were pantries, maid's room, laundry rooms and storage rooms (51).

Racial situations and reactions have come up at many places in the narrative. Biju had inherited feelings of 'Nationality' and hatred for subjugating "white world". In New York, Biju felt tormented by the thoughtless commercialism, rampant racism and rapacious ruin perpetuated by the neo-colonial exploitation. He eventually came back to India. His life in 'America was full of hardships.

Tired of hopping from one job to another, he decided either to go back to India or to get all elusive green cards. In the USA, the illegal immigrants lost their identities. Regarding this Dr. Rajni Singh opines:

Migration is a realistic pain and a deplorable situation of illegal immigrants in the USA... Every character of novel persuades, but in reality he has not received anything, nevertheless he loses whatever he gets in his life (200)

Biju was walking on the thorny and ticklish path in New York. He thought over the happy days, he had spent with his father in Kalimpong. Biju felt the past days in India were jubilant and he thought that he walked on bed of roses during those days. Biju pondered:

How powerful our village is. How good the roti tastes there! It is because the atta is ground by hand, not by machine ... and because it is made on a choobash, better than anything cooked on a gas or on kerosene stove (103)

At Gandhi Café in New York, Harish Harry, the owner of the café told him how he could not afford money to him for his medical expenses. He pointed an accusing finger at Biju and told him that he was responsible for breaking his leg. He blamed him of not being careful and said:

You should have to pay me for not cleaning living like a pig. Am I telling you to live like a pig? You can help cutting the vegetables while lying down and if you are not better, go home. Doctors are very cheap and good in India (188-189)

Kiran Desai brought out Biju's pitiable condition by the image of the dead insect. It was ironical to see that the restaurant workers in America could at least relish daintly dishes, no matter even if it was at the cost of their own country. Biju was sick of the fork and knife, the everyday difficulties, the green card desire and the daily assaults of the restaurant owners. Biju decided to go back to India with his little savings. But misfortune was waiting for him in Kalimpong. He was robbed off his belongings. But misfortune was waiting for Biju in Kalimpong. He was robbed off his belongings, money and even his American dress.

Kiran Desai used "irony" as one of the devices to highlight the theme of the novel. Biju and his father made all attempts right and wrong to get American Visa for Biju. The cook obtained a fake passport with the hope of bright future. He was proud to announce he was the father of a boy in America. He even recommended some boys for jobs in America. Kiran Desai used the symbol of idle insect to explain the condition of Biju in America, because his hopes were devastated.

Whether India or America, human beings cannot fulfill their dreams and that is what the novel tried to say. Cook's dream was to see his only son become an American. Sai's dream rested on her lover Gyan. Biju's only dream was to earn wealth. But nobody's dream was fulfilled till the end. That is the reason why Kiran Desai titled this novel as *The Inheritance of Loss*

Of late people have craze for visiting and working in abroad. They enter into a new nation, dreaming that it will be raining gold there. But when they meet with plenty of problems there, they start feeling that, "it is raining rats". This aspect is focused by Kiran Desai in this novel, through the character Biju.

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